

Fig. 1. David Rothenberg, *Svalbard*, 2009, crediti fotografici Andrea Galvani. Courtesy David Rothenberg

Listening to the Anthropocene. Sound deterritorializations in contemporary art

Elmira Sharipova

The concept of the Anthropocene has become fundamental to understanding the planetary transformations currently underway. Proposed by atmospheric chemist Paul Crutzen and biologist Eugene Stoermer in 2000, the term defines a new geological epoch in which human activity exerts a dominant influence on Earth's systems, altering the atmosphere, modifying the biosphere, and redefining ecological balances. Crossing the boundaries of the natural sciences, the Anthropocene has become a crucial interpretative device for the humanities and social sciences, stimulating profound reflection on the interconnections between human and non-human, technology and ecology, responsibility and sustainability. Within this landscape, some research has also highlighted the acoustic dimension of anthropogenic impact, helping to outline a *Sonic Anthropocene*. This approach traces a critical cartography of the sound transformations induced by human action: noise pollution, the loss of auditory biodiversity, and alterations in acoustic ecosystems reveal not only the human footprint, but also the vulnerability of species whose survival depends on

sound. It is here that sound art, rather than establishing itself as mere documentation, takes the form of a deterritorializing practice, according to the definition of Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari³. By deconstructing sensory hierarchies, unlike codified music, it redefines ecological connections, transforming sound into a relational medium that makes otherwise abstract environmental dynamics perceptible⁴.

In this perspective, *field recording*⁵ transcends its traditional function of 'capturing' the soundscape to become a tool for revealing underlying ecological tensions: the recording of an ecosystem in the process of extinction is not simply a documentary archive, but a political act that critically questions the role of human intervention in its progressive disappearance. This conceptual reconfiguration is intertwined with new materialism and posthumanism, attributing to sound an autonomous agency that transcends its traditional subordination to human perception. As Adam Svec observes, through sound we can rethink the very idea of voice and individual expression: sound becomes a relational entity that propagates and transforms itself through different bodies and experiences, creating unexpected connections between the human and the non-human.

At the same time, Vadim Keylin highlights the political implications, showing how participatory sound practices generate spaces for collective agency, opposing the extractive logic of the Anthropocene and including non-human actors in an ecology of participation⁷. Salomé Voegelin further radicalizes the approach and proposes a conception of the acoustic phenomenon as privileged epistemological material for exploring the thresholds between human and non-human⁸. Sound materiality emerges as an intra-active event co-produced through

towards the situated practice of listening. The invitation to dig into the acoustic dimension represents an immersion into its transformative traces, which destabilize the subject-object dualism. Drawing on Karen Barad's *agential realism*, Voegelin theorizes sound matter as generative *intra-action* that produces worlds and opens up spaces of political possibility beyond the visual-representational domain. This perspective is further elaborated in Brandon LaBelle's text, which develops a poetics of listening understood as a practice of resistance, intertwining the principles of Jane Bennett's *vibrant materialism* with an aesthetic capable of valuing fragility and vulnerability as transformative forces. LaBelle elaborates an ethic of acoustic fragility, in which elements such as a trembling voice, imperfect echo, or minimal noise become vectors of political agency. Thus, following a theoretical line close to that of Bennett, sound is not conceived simply as a message or aesthetic object, but rather as vibrant, relational, and affective matter, capable of activating connections, disrupting sensory hierarchies, and generating unexpected alliances. According to LaBelle, sound matter is therefore to be understood as weak, affective, disturbing, and relational, a presence that, precisely in its opacity and vulnerability, resists capture and allows the formation of what he calls *unlikely publics*¹³. These publics emerge on the margins of official modes of political and social representation, building dissensual solidarity through fragile and unspectacular sound practices. This vision translates into artistic experiences that favor minimal sound installations, moments of shared listening, and discreet and elusive acoustic strategies, thus defining listening itself as a form of ethical and political responsibility towards otherness, both human and non-human.

Sound deterritorialization and critical thinking. Sound genealogies from Deleuze and Guattari to Kim-Cohen

Recent literature on Sound Studies has found in the thinking of Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari, particularly in their work *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*¹⁴, fundamental conceptual tools for understanding contemporary sound art practices. Two notions emerge as particularly influential: the *return* and *deterritorialization*. For the two philosophers, sound has a unique ability to escape pre-established structures. Unlike other more easily codifiable forms of expression, sound moves, transforms, contaminates, and crosses boundaries. This fluid and mobile nature gives it what Deleuze and Guattari call the power of *deterritorialization*: the ability to undo existing territories in order to create new ones, to dissolve established codes in order to generate new connections¹⁵. The concept of *the refrain* becomes central to understanding how sound operates in art. It is not a simple melodic repetition, but a complex device that philosophers describe through the metaphor of the prism: just as a crystal refracts light in multiple directions, so the refrain acts on the surrounding space-time, generating vibrations, decompositions and transformations. The refrain creates sound territories—think of a bird's song delimiting its own space—but simultaneously dissolves and reconfigures them. This territorial dynamic of sound allows Deleuze and Guattari to trace a profound continuity between natural phenomena and musical creation. Human music does not oppose the sounds of nature but shares the same constitutive ambivalence: on the one hand, it constructs recognizable sound worlds, and on the other, it continuously destabilizes them. The reference to birdsong

Fig. 2. David Rothenberg, *Diagram of Interspecies Performance with Humpback Whales*, Hawaii, 2007. Courtesy David Rothenberg

which runs through the history of Western music – from Jannequin to Messiaen – is therefore not a simple example of imitation, but indicates how music has always been porous with respect to the non-human forces that pass through it¹⁷. In its most advanced state, according to Deleuze and Guattari, music operates a "molecularization of sound material" and a "cosmicization of forces" that connects sound to a universal dimension¹⁸. This conception of sound as malleable and deterritorialized matter has opened up new trajectories of understanding and experimentation in Anthropocene Sound Studies.

Drawing inspiration from the concepts of *refrain* and *deterritorialization*, Louisa Collenberg offers an analysis of the intersection between experimental music, philosophy, and animal studies, focusing on the works of artist-musician and philosopher David Rothenberg. His

This investigation is part of the contemporary debate on sound art as a medium for rethinking the relationship between humans and non-humans. Rothenberg stands out for his exploration of sound ecology and interspecies musical interactions, in which sound becomes a relational device for overcoming barriers between species and cultures. Central to Rothenberg's work are his musical collaborations with animals, which exemplify a posthuman approach to listening (fig. 1). In the *Whale Music* project (2008), Rothenberg plays the clarinet in dialogue with the songs of humpback whales¹⁹, creating a form of interspecies improvisation that transcends the conventions of human music²⁰(fig. 2). This 'duet' does not aim to imitate or anthropomorphize the sounds of humpback whales, but to establish a sonic connection that, as Deleuze's concept of *refrain* suggests

Fig. 3. David Rothenberg, *Jamming with Brood X Cicadas*, 2011, Lake Springfield, IL, photo credit Charles Lindsay. Courtesy David Rothenberg

and Guattari, territorializes and deterritorializes acoustic space, intertwining the human and non-human in a dynamic relationship. Similarly, in *Bug Music: How Insects Gave Us Rhythm and Noise* (2013), Rothenberg explores the cyclical rhythms of insects, such as the song of cicadas, to trace an evolutionary continuity between the sound expressions of different species²¹ (fig. 3).

In the project *Nightingales in Berlin: Searching for the Perfect Sound* (2019), Rothenberg exemplifies the potential of sound art in the Anthropocene, exploring the tension between nature and the urban environment through musical improvisations with nightingales in parks.

chi berlinesi²². His performances promote collective listening that sensitizes the audience to coexistence with the non-human, embodying deterritorialized listening. Jazz, displaced from its conventional club setting, is reinserted into a hybrid space where nature and city overlap. The artist does not seek to imitate birds or impose human musical structures on them; rather, through improvisation, he explores what he himself defines as a feeling-with: a way of temporarily inhabiting another sensibility, not to appropriate it, but to open up to "new possibilities for interaction"²³. Collenberg

He keenly understands how these practices generate what, following Deleuze and Guattari, we can call a rhizomatic sound territory, a temporary and porous acoustic space where hierarchies between species momentarily dissolve²⁴. This is not a matter of romanticizing nature or anthropomorphizing animals, but of recognizing in sound a force capable of creating transversal connections, of opening up areas of indeterminacy, where humans and non-humans can meet on a relatively equal footing²⁵.

This vision resonates deeply with the thinking of François Bonnet, who sees sound as a privileged means of accessing what verbal language cannot reach; a field of metamorphosis where new worlds can emerge²⁶. Rothenberg's practice embodies this philosophy in an exemplary way: by accepting the risk of failure, involuntary dissonances, and sudden silences as integral parts of interspecies dialogue, the composer proposes an ethic of listening based on mutual vulnerability rather than control. In this sense, his work offers a possible response to the challenges of the Anthropocene: not through domination or separation, but through forms of creative coexistence that sound, in its vibrant materiality, makes possible.

However, the adoption of Deleuzian concepts such as *rhizome* and *deterritorialization* is not without criticism. Seth Kim-Cohen questions the indiscriminate use of Deleuzian thought in contemporary Sound Studies, highlighting how these terms are often used to legitimize fluid and immersive practices that lack a solid theoretical framework: "The rhizome suggests a liquidity that leaks and seeps in all directions—a kind of ambient flux"²⁷. According to him, this aesthetic typology, defined as *ambience*, in fascinating

the senses end up numbing critical faculties. Far from celebrating sensory intensity as a potentially subversive force, the scholar denounces the mythology of pure sound, interpreting it as a form of retreat from theoretical confrontation and perceptual complacency: "Politics is not ambient. It is disruptive, confrontational, insistent"²⁸. If for Deleuze and Guattari the *rhizome* represents a proliferating network of free connections, capable of escaping hierarchical structures, for Kim-Cohen it risks being reduced to an aestheticizing and weakened metaphor. As he ironically observes, the Deleuzian mantra "E... E... E..."²⁹ may suggest an open and infinitely inclusive structure, but it often ends up eluding conflict, distinction, and taking a stand, which are indispensable elements of any effective artistic-political practice³⁰.

Biophony and ecological listening: Bernie Krause

Bernie Krause stands out as a pioneering figure in acoustic ecology, having developed a revolutionary perspective on the relationship between sound, ecology, and culture. Moving from electronic music to recording natural sounds in the 1970s, Krause introduced the concept of *biophony*³¹, or the collection of sounds produced by living organisms in an ecosystem. This term joins *geophony* (non-biological natural sounds, such as wind) and *anthropophony* (sounds of human origin), offering a conceptual framework for analyzing the complexity of soundscapes. Another of his fundamental contributions is *the acoustic niche hypothesis*, according to which each species evolves to occupy a distinct sound frequency, minimizing communication interference³³. This insight highlights the role of sound in the

Figs. 4 and 5.
Bernie Krause and
United Visual Artists, *The
Great Animal
Orchestra*, 2016.
Exhibition view of *The
Great Animal
Orchestra*, Fondation
Cartier pour l'art
contemporain, Paris, 2016.
Collection of the Fondation
Cartier pour l'art contemporain
(acquired 2017). Photo
credit: Luc Boegly.

Courtesy Bernie
Krause, United Visual Artists
and Fondation
Cartier pour l'art
contemporain

ecological balance, opening up new perspectives on biodiversity³⁴.

The Great Animal Orchestra installation

(2016-2017)³⁵, presented at the Fondation Cartier in Paris, represents the culmination of her research. The work, which includes over five thousand hours of recordings from fifteen thousand species, immerses the audience in natural soundscapes, ranging from dawn choruses in forests to the sea songs of whales.

The project does more than simply document: by comparing historical recordings with recent sounds, Krause highlights the disappearance of animal voices due to deforestation, noise pollution, and climate change. This approach

transforms sound into a critical device that makes the invisible audible – the loss of biodiversity – and challenges anthropocentric narratives that relegate nature to a passive background (fig. 4).

³⁶ The installation unfolds in a large darkened space, where visitors are invited to sit or walk slowly, surrounded by natural sounds played through a high-quality audio system (fig. 5).

These sounds, which Krause defines as *biophony*, represent the 'orchestrations' of nature, in which each species contributes its own unique 'instrument'. The effect is that of a natural symphony that evolves in real time, transporting visitors to distant and

often threatened by human activity³⁷. Vinciane Despret offers an in-depth analysis of *The Great Animal Orchestra*, recognizing Krause's contribution as a challenge to traditional scientific methodologies based on visual observation and cataloging³⁸. Despret highlights how his approach is more akin to that of a composer or musician, as he does not limit himself to recording individual sounds, but seeks to capture the way in which animals and natural elements compose a collective harmony together.

A central aspect of Despret's analysis is the parallelism between the natural orchestra described by Krause and political and social theories, particularly those of Thomas Hobbes and Bruno Latour³⁹. Using the metaphor of the orchestra, the philosopher suggests that the model of

natural sound composition offers a new perspective on the possible organization of human societies, based on cooperation and mutual attention rather than competition and hierarchy.

Despret also explores the philosophical implications of Krause's work, particularly how an approach focused on the acoustic dimension can transform our understanding of the world, emphasizing how attention to sound reveals the animation and vitality of the natural world in ways that the scopic mode may not capture. This aspect is fundamental because it decentralizes the optical sense that dominates human sensory experience. Despret wonders what would change if we replaced the visual dimension, which has always been privileged, with the sonic one

sound. If the act of seeing allows us to distinguish the contours of the body, creating an image of the world based on the cognition of autonomous entities, sound is localized by our senses in a more complex way, thus broadening the spectrum of perceived reality⁴⁰.

Alongside Despret's philosophical perspective, Mark Peter Wright makes a critical contribution. Wright recognizes Krause's pioneering role in the field of sound ecology, crediting him with establishing a practice of systematic listening to soundscapes, capable of highlighting the interconnection between species through their collective 'voices'⁴¹. However, in *The Great Animal Orchestra*, the metaphor of nature as a symphony—although effective in describing the acoustic complexity of ecosystems—is criticized by Wright for its adherence to an anthropocentric imaginary⁴². The musical analogy, in fact, applies typically human romantic and virtuosic filters to nature, reducing biodiversity to a 'composition' to be recorded, cataloged, and enjoyed aesthetically. According to Wright, this method reproduces a colonial logic, in which humans set themselves up as curators and privileged listeners, rather than recognizing themselves as part of a network of multispecies relationships⁴³. The orchestral metaphor, while evocative, thus risks perpetuating a cultural model that objectifies nature, rather than deconstructing human-nonhuman hierarchies.

Another critical issue raised by Wright concerns the idealization of nature conveyed by Krause's environmental recordings. He observes how such practices, often curated and edited to emphasize biotic harmony, end up constructing an image of nature as orderly and separate, while neglecting the dissonant and hybrid components that characterize the soundscapes of the Anthropocene. This aestheticization, writes Wright, applies a "romantic and virtuoso filter" to the reality of sound, obscuring its ecological and material tensions. This idealization contrasts with contemporary ecocritical and posthumanist perspectives, which emphasize the dissonant and hybrid components of soundscapes.

and virtuosic filter" to sonic reality, obscuring its ecological and material tensions⁴⁴. This idealization contrasts with contemporary ecocritical and posthumanist perspectives, which reject the nature/culture dichotomy, proposing instead a relational and interconnected vision. Wright draws on the thinking of Donna Haraway, in particular the concept of *entanglement*, to affirm the need to recognize the constitutive intertwining of human, non-human, and technology, rather than maintaining binary and romantic distinctions that perpetuate an essentialist view of nature⁴⁵.

Sound archiving and biodiversity loss: David Monacchi and Anna Lockwood

The work of Italian composer, artist, and researcher David Monacchi develops in dialogue with Krause's *acoustic niche hypothesis*. However, while Krause uses biophonic recordings primarily as documentary tools for the contemporary ecological crisis and as catalysts for environmental activism, Monacchi expands their epistemological and aesthetic scope, transforming them into innovative creative paradigms. His method is based on the idea of respectful human intervention, which fills the acoustic 'voids' left by other species 'as an exercise and metaphor for non-destructive collaboration with an existing sound ecosystem'⁴⁶. This is not just a creative gesture, but an ethical stance which, in the artist's words, 'is one of respect: one does not enter into this acoustic complexity in order to subvert its proportions, symmetries, counterbalances, and tempos'⁴⁷; a principle that characterizes the entire practice of *ecoacoustic composition*⁴⁸. This approach not only constitutes a methodological evolution with respect to previous practices of interaction with soundscapes

natural, but also redefines the artist's ethical position within the global acoustic ecosystem.

The *Fragments of Extinction* project (1998-ongoing)⁴⁹ embodies this vision. Through three-dimensional recordings conducted in the equatorial forests of Africa, South America, and Asia, Monacchi captures the sounds of primary ecosystems threatened by anthropogenic expansion, with the aim of preserving the sound heritage of environments at risk of extinction. Using advanced technologies and high-definition microphones, the artist creates *sound portraits* that faithfully reproduce natural acoustic spatiality, offering an aesthetic experience combined with scientific research on ecoacoustics. Monacchi highlights how sound, more than other sensory indicators, allows us to detect the dynamics of change in ecosystems at an early stage. Listening therefore becomes an essential sensitive tool for revealing otherwise invisible environmental transformations, aided by spectrographic analysis of soundscapes, which, by visualizing imperceptible frequencies and densities, makes it possible to observe ecological changes.

A distinctive feature of the artist's project is the *Bio-Acoustic Theater*, which constitutes an immersive evolution, culminating in the design of a *Sonosphere*, a patented three-dimensional acoustic theater that faithfully reproduces the sound structure of complex ecosystems. With its spherical architecture and high-resolution speaker system, the *Sonosphere* does not merely reproduce sounds but creates an all-encompassing environment capable of reactivating perceptive empathy with acoustic biodiversity. Unlike Krause's documentary approach, which falls within the realm of *Soundscape Ecology*, Monacchi transforms the soundscape into a performative practice capable of directly engaging the audience's hearing, imagination, and

the ecological consciousness of the audience. This work is part of a transition from anthropocentrism to an emerging ecocentrism, where biodiversity is no longer recognized as a simple 'resource' but as an interconnected network of existences.

Fragments of Extinction can be interpreted through the lens of Deleuze and Guattari's *detrterritorialization*, revealing deep tensions between aesthetics, technology, and power. The very act of recording sounds in equatorial ecosystems accomplishes a movement of *detrterritorialization*: soundscapes, conceived as flows of intensity and relationships, are dislodged from their original ecological milieu through the process of technological acquisition performed by high-definition microphones. As observed by the two French philosophers, this process is not limited to a simple displacement, but involves decoding: a living environment, comparable to a *body without organs*⁵⁰ – a field of forces without a predetermined hierarchical structure – is transformed into codified matter, translated into spectrograms and digital archives. The subsequent re-territorialization in *the Sonosphere*, a three-dimensional acoustic space, represents a paradox: while for Deleuze and Guattari *detrterritorialization* opens up new planes of proliferating consistency, here sound is re-inscribed in a closed and hyper-realistic technological environment. Rather than liberating new perceptual possibilities, the *Sonosphere* risks crystallizing ecological complexity into a consumable, museumized form accompanied by a controlled aesthetic experience.

Wright describes this space as an "elsewhere ^{field}", a mediated non-place that neutralizes the political potential of sound, privileging passive contemplation over critical listening. Technological fidelity, however extraordinary, re-

Fig. 6. Anna Lockwood, recording on the Hudson River north of New York, 2020, photo credits Sam Green. Courtesy Anna Lockwood and Sam Green

reduces sound biodiversity to a consumable cultural product, an operation that dampens sound's ability to destabilize dominant narratives about nature. Finally, the project raises postcolonial questions: the choice to record forests in the Global South risks replicating a colonial logic, transforming sound biodiversity into an 'exotic archive' for consumption in the Global North. Monacchi's access to ecologically contested spaces, mediated by technologies such as *Sonosfera*, raises questions about who has the right to archive these sounds and how indigenous communities are represented in this process. While Monacchi operates within a logic of conservation—albeit problematic—

New Zealand composer and sound artist Anna Lockwood places herself in an open temporal dimension, rejecting the fixity of the archive in favor of an idea of sound as event, flow, and ecological infrascription. Lockwood's works are part of a constellation of contemporary acoustic practices that interrogate the Anthropocene from an affective, ecological, and posthuman perspective. In her *Sound Maps*—large-scale sound projects that map entire river systems through meticulous environmental recordings and oral testimonies—the aquatic landscape emerges not as a mere acoustic object, but as a complex relational subject, endowed with agency and memory

⁵². Starting with *A Sound Map of the Hudson River* (1982)⁵³, continuing with *A Sound Map of the Danube* (2005)⁵⁴, and up to the most recent *A Sound Map of the Housatonic River* (2010)⁵⁵, Lockwood constructs a river archive that does not freeze reality, but restores its vibrations, mutations, and cultural and political resonances (fig. 6). In the case of the Danube, the river crosses linguistic and geocultural boundaries, becoming a vector of oral histories, conflicts, and ecological memories. The artist asks the inhabitants: "What does the river mean to you? Could you live without it?"⁵⁶. The answers collected, integrated into multichannel installations, are not simple testimonies, but elements of a sensitive cartography, where sound and care, ecology and relationships intertwine.

The uniqueness of his approach lies in the use of close-up microphones and hydrophones, which deliberately forego any pretense of documentary neutrality in favor of an immersive and embodied listening experience. The resulting multi-channel installations offer a non-hierarchical listening experience, where sounds circulate freely in the exhibition space, simultaneously evoking a geological time and an affective dimension. This practice aligns with what Wright calls "listening-with," a situated and responsible listening that challenges the idea of the soundscape as an object to be captured.

Lockwood's poetics are also distinguished by a rigorous rejection of intrusive editing and any aesthetics of sound spectacularization:

"I need to remove myself from the river and from you as much as possible—so minimal editing is about removing myself from the process so you're not aware of its being a composition."

The artist's practice thus embodies a form of acoustic humility, where the technique of recording and composition is not configured as an act of control, but as a gesture of openness and availability to the sonic otherness of the natural world. However, the artist does not exclude the human element, but reintegrates it into the ecosystemic network: "We need to recognize how deeply integrated we are with our environment"⁵⁸. This statement resonates deeply with the relational ontology proposed by Bennett, where human and non-human are intertwined in vibrant material 'assemblages'.

In Lockwood's most recent projects (see *A Sound Map of the Housatonic River*), a political dimension emerges more clearly, acting indirectly and avoiding the rhetoric of explicit denunciation:

"Out of that may come some sort of caring about the river, and then out of that some sort of awareness of issues like pollution, conservation, and access to water."

This strategy suggests a form of acoustic ecology that operates primarily on the level of the sensible and the invisible, generating an affective space of listening rather than a coded message.

Sound intra-actions as revelations of the invisible: Jana Winderen and Christina Kubisch

Beyond memory, sound reveals what escapes ordinary perception, dissolving the boundaries between the natural and the technological. Jana Winderen, a Norwegian sound artist with a background in marine biology, mathematics, and chemistry, uses hydrophone recordings and immersive installations to

Fig. 7. Jana Winderen, *Sound Field Recording in Iceland*, 2014, photo credits Finnbogí Petursson. Courtesy Jana Winderen

making underwater ecosystems audible. His compositions, which capture the submerged vocalizations of the ocean depths and the cryogenic vibrations of Arctic ice, do not merely document the environmental crisis, but articulate a form of *deterritorialized listening* that decentralizes anthropocentric narratives and invites a sensory immersion into non-human sound universes (fig. 7). The artist employs sophisticated recording technologies—ultrasensitive hydrophones, ultrasound detectors, contact microphones—to capture acoustic phenomena beyond the threshold of human perception: the microclicks of crustaceans, the intricate sound structures of marine mammals, or the subtle crackling of planktonic microorganisms (fig. 8). In *The Noisiest Guys on the Planet* (2010), Winderen explores the acoustic universe of decapods, focusing conceptually

on the pistol shrimp (*Alpheus heterochilus*), a creature capable of producing, through the snapping of its oversized claw, a sonic explosion that reaches the impressive intensity of 210 dB, a sound power that exceeds that of a jet taking off⁶⁰. This ability subverts traditional ontological hierarchies, revealing forms of 'sonic warfare' that are not exclusively human: "Weaponry, baffle, camouflage, and decoy are exclusive to neither visual culture nor the human alone." Stefan Helmreich points out that Winderen recreates a multispecies soundscape, in which the underwater dimension becomes an experimental laboratory, testifying to the growing role of humans as direct agents in ecosystem transformation⁶². A more in-depth analysis of the formal structure of the work is offered by Wri-

Fig. 8. Jana Winderen, *Hydrophone Recording Fifteen Meters Under the Sea Ice by the North Pole*, 2015, photo credits Foundation Mamont. Courtesy Jana Winderen

ght, who highlights a crucial element: the sound composition deliberately opens with the mechanical noise of a marine engine. This initial moment is not a simple documentary convention or a marginal detail, but represents a significant conceptual threshold that radically problematizes the romantic notion of uncontaminated immersion in non-human environments. As Wright observes: "Crossing audible borders, therefore, disrupts the myth of 'being there' that site-based listening promotes." Thus, a complex dialectical relationship is established between the human and non-human dimensions, revealing how contemporary underwater soundscapes are already inevitably modulated and permeated by human activity. Any fantasy of primordial acoustic purity is therefore removed.

A complementary approach emerges in the work *The Wanderer* (2015), where Winderen develops a more refined and meditative composition based on underwater recordings that generate an immersive and multisensory listening experience (fig. 9). According to Salomé Voegelin, the work does not merely reveal an acoustic dimension of the underwater landscape, but puts into practice an epistemological practice of listening, capable of destabilizing the visual imagination of localization and constructing a situated presence that exceeds visual representation⁶⁴. The acoustic landscape is not mapped, but experienced in its dynamic opacity: "the world comes to voice in the shared space between listener and sound"⁶⁵. Here, sound does not represent, but 'intra-acts': a performative force that makes the co-constitution of environments, bodies, and technologies perceptible.

Fig. 9. Jana Winderen, *Listening to Find Questions*, performance/talk at Sonar Festival, Barcelona, 2023. Courtesy Jana Winderen

This articulation is also taken up by Stefan Helmreich, who reads Winderen's work in light of an epistemological transformation of the field into a laboratory. In *Heated* (2008), the artist records the warming of the oceans, treating the marine environment as an empirical-sonic space: her compositions, Helmreich states, are not simple landscapes, but "auditory documents gathered from research trips, treated as improvisational ^{material}." The immersion proposed by Winderen is therefore not a contemplative descent, but a technical and theoretical procedure mediated by transduction, which defines a *cyborg sensibility* capable of expanding listening beyond natural perception⁶⁷.

Works such as *Energy Field* (2010) further expand this approach, focusing on the fragility of Arctic and ocean ecosystems through recordings

made in the Barents Sea, Greenland, and Norway. Here, Winderen captures the sounds of crustaceans, fish, and marine organisms in their natural habitat, creating an immersive sound experience that reveals the delicacy of cold environments and their ecological vulnerability.

In a complementary way, with *Electrical Walks* (2003-ongoing), German sound artist and composer Christina Kubisch explores the electromagnetic sounds of cities, inviting us to reflect on how technology has radically transformed our relationship with the environment, both visually and acoustically, and questioning our perception of what is natural and what is artificial. The work *Electrical Walks* consists of a series of urban walks in which participants, equipped with magnetic headphones designed by the artist, intercept electromagnetic signals emitted by devices such as

Figs. 10-12. Christina Kubisch, *Electrical Walks Paris*, 2019, Gaité Lyrique, *Suono Inudito* exhibition. Christina Kubisch, *Electrical Walks Prague*, 2022, Kunstshalle Praha, *Kinetismus* exhibition. Christina Kubisch, *Electrical Walks Chemnitz*, 2022, Wirkbau, Pochen Festival. Photo credits Christina Kubisch. Courtesy Christina Kubisch

ATMs (fig. 10), traffic lights, and Wi-Fi networks, which are translated into soundscapes that can be listened to (figs. 11-12). Far from being an immersive experience for its own sake, the work unmasks the hidden technological infrastructures that permeate contemporary life. As Kubisch states: "I never point a finger and say, 'This is bad' or 'This is good'. I'm more interested in having people recognize what's around them by doing it ^{themselves}."

This choice explicitly rejects avant-garde didacticism and the logic of direct activism in favor of what Vadim Keylin defines as "politics as experience": an implicit, open, and contingent politics capable of stimulating relational and situated awareness in the listener⁷⁰. As Keylin points out, this artistic modality configures *Electrical Walks* as a paradigmatic example of an "augmented acoustic environment," in which acoustic perception is mediated by technologies that extend or alter the range of human hearing

Keylin points out, this artistic modality configures *Electrical Walks* as a paradigmatic example of an "augmented acoustic environment," in which acoustic perception is mediated by technologies that extend or redefine reality⁷¹. Kubisch, in fact, does not add new sounds to the environment, but rather makes phenomena that are normally imperceptible to humans accessible through the technique of electromagnetic induction. Yet understanding *Electrical Walks* goes beyond mere experiential enjoyment. As Seth Kim-Cohen observes, interpreting Kubisch's project exclusively as a phenomenological experience would risk falling into the "fantasy of completeness," in the illusion that reality can be fully restored through sensory translation

. The city that Kubisch makes perceptible through sound is not an organic, unified body to be explored sensorially, but rather a complex set of fragmentary signals and meanings, decoded through an informational paradigm different from the original one. In Kubisch's works, listening thus becomes a deeply participatory and relational act, in which the audience takes an active role in deconstructing sensory rhetoric, transforming the acoustic experience into a critical reflection on the limits and possibilities of our perceptions in the contemporary urban context.

Post-natural imagination: Mark Peter Wright and Angus Carlyle

Sound art goes even further than documentation and revelation to create completely new sound ecologies. Scholars and artist-musicians Mark Peter Wright and Angus Carlyle, in their project *Decoys* (2021), open this reflection with an innovative approach that intertwines geology, geography and anthropology. Criticizing the dominant visual representations of the Anthropocene—often reduced to *cathartic images of catastrophe*—they propose a sonic alternative based on Ursula Le Guin's *geolinguistics*⁷⁴. *Decoys* is a sound composition released on vinyl (LP format) that transports the listener to a 'scorched earth' scenario, with a post-apocalyptic landscape populated by a more-than-human figure, defined in Wright's text as the 'Noisy-Nonselself protagonist'⁷⁵ (fig. 13)⁷⁶. The notion of *decoy* (bait, simulacrum) takes on a central critical function in the work. This mimetic gesture does not aim to faithfully

reality, but rather to generate fragile and unstable interpretations of it, recalling the idea of *the decoy* as a device that disorients and challenges perception. As pointed out by Wright and Carlyle, *De-coys* stages acoustic landscapes created through *Foley art* techniques, evoking post-natural environments using residual materials such as polystyrene, aluminum foil, magnetic tapes, and fans (fig. 14). This process of sound construction takes the form of a sonic deterritorialization in which the territory of nature, traditionally codified as separate, pure, and authentic, is dismantled through *Foley*, which exposes its cultural construction, while sound becomes a 'refrain' that blurs the boundaries between reality and fiction, nature and artifice, opening up to an aesthetic speculation that exceeds anthropocentric categories. A central aspect of *Decoys* is its critique of sonic authenticity, a theme that Wright links to the use of *foley* in nature documentaries, such as those produced by the BBC (*Frozen Planet*⁷⁸, *Planet Earth II*⁷⁹, *Seven Worlds One Planet*⁸⁰), which routinely use *Foley art* techniques to artificially recreate environmental and animal sounds. These sounds, produced in the studio, are then presented as if they were real field recordings, contributing to an illusion of 'natural authenticity' that Wright considers highly problematic: seemingly 'natural' sounds, such as the rustling of snow, thunder, rain, or animal footprints, are actually generated in the studio by artificial means: "Thunder is a piece of tin foil. Rain is the sound of frying bacon. Cornstarch is analogous to snow underfoot"⁸¹. In other cases, animal sounds are arbitrarily relocated to habitats to which they do not belong:

Fig. 13. Mark Peter Wright, Angus Carlyle, *Decoys, score*, inside cover of the LP, 2018, photo credits multi. modal. Courtesy Angus Carlyle and Mark Peter Wright

Fig. 14. Mark Peter Wright, Angus Carlyle, *Foley Studio Work*, 2018, photo credits Carlyle, Wright. Courtesy Angus Carlyle and Mark Peter Wright

Fig. 15. Mark Peter Wright, *The Noisy-Nonselfor, I, the Thing in the Margins*, 2019, photo credits Mark Peter Wright. Courtesy Mark Peter Wright

“a bear call onto the wrong species of bear. Similarly, the call of a site-specific bird was dubbed onto a location it had never been resident of”⁸².

Furthermore, Wright points out that many of these practices are not disclosed or are hidden from the public, who are thus led to believe in the truth of the material presented. An emblematic case of the artificial construction of authenticity in nature documentaries is represented by a scene from the series *Frozen Planet* (2011), which shows a female polar bear giving birth to her cubs. The images suggest that the event is taking place in the wild Arctic environment, when in fact the sequence was filmed in a Dutch zoo. This information is not communicated in the narrative of the episode, but only appears in the supplementary material and special features on the DVD, thus creating a disconnect between perceptual experience and production truth. This raises ethical questions about the responsibility of the media, especially when it comes to the portrayal of animals.

, but only appears in the supplementary materials and special features on the DVD, thus creating a disconnect between the viewer’s perception and the truth of the production. This raises ethical questions about the responsibility of the media, especially when it comes to environmental education.

Wright’s criticism is not limited to denouncing manipulative techniques, but extends to an entire ideology of environmental realism. According to him, it is a form of *aesthetic greenwashing*: the BBC contributes to an idealized environmental imaginary, presenting nature as a separate, remote, harmonious, and uncontaminated space. This narrative obscures the reality of the Anthropocene, made up of ecological crises, contamination, urban noise, and anthropogenic interference. *Decoys* is a performative and theoretical response to the aesthetics of naturalistic hyperrealism

: a work that does not mask artifice but exposes it, and which uses noise, understood not only as sound but as epistemic interference, as a tool to defuse the illusory promise of authenticity (fig. 15). In this sense, the entire operation presents itself as a sonic counter-discourse to the dominant documentary ideology.

At the heart of Wright's reflection on *field recording* stands the figure of *the Noisy-Nonsel*, protagonist of the *Decoys* project (2018) and central conceptual figure in the volume *Listening After Nature* (fig. 16). The *Noisy-Nonsel* is a hybrid, acoustic, and visual being, constructed from technological debris and residual materials (magnetic tape, polystyrene, mud, aluminum foil) and activated through *Foley art* techniques in closed recording environments. This entity, conceived

Like a *hybrid Doppelgänger*⁸⁴, it emerges from the 'taciturn stories' of environmental sound engineers and takes the form of a chimerical and unstable identity, capable of generating ethical and epistemological disorientation. The *Noisy-Nonsel*, writes Wright, is a 'monstrous auditory identity', a theoretical artifact that consumes and is consumed, present yet elusive, familiar yet alienating: a residual emanation of the technical and cultural gesture of field recording⁸⁵.

Through this narrative and sonic strategy, *Decoys* offers a deconstructive critique of the rhetoric of acoustic realism and the aesthetics of high fidelity. Where the BBC promised the auditory truth of nature 'out there', *Decoys* proposes a fabricated, unstable, and situated world in which listening is always impure, and precisely for this reason politically productive. The work

Fig. 16. Mark Peter Wright, *The Noisy-Nonsel* or, *I, the Thing in the Margins*, IMT Gallery, London, 2015, photo credits Mark Peter Wright. Courtesy Mark Peter Wright

does not describe an environment, but constructs a fictitious aural territory, which, paradoxically, is more sincere than many field recordings. In this context, *Noisy-Nonself* proves to be a perfect example of the fourth phase of the third order of the simulacrum theorized by Jean Baudrillard in *Simulacra and Simulation* (2024): no longer a copy of reality, nor a mask that hides its absence, but an image that no longer has any referent, an autonomy of the sign that replaces the real with its operational double⁸⁶. *Noisy-Nonself* does not represent nature, but mimics its technical production, anticipates its non-existence, making audible the emptiness of any attempt at environmental realism.

The sound practice of Mark Peter Wright and Angus Carlyle, like the others discussed here, reveals a significant transformation in the conception of sound, which from a perceptual element becomes a tool for investigating ecological and social relationships. This shift from documentation to deconstruction marks the emergence of a critical consciousness: sound is no longer a neutral witness, but a field of forces in which ecological, colonial, and ontological conflicts converge. What unites seemingly heterogeneous practices such as those just analyzed is the rejection of any original purity. Sound ceases to be an archive or document and becomes a territory to be inhabited collectively, a vibrant space in which humans and non-humans negotiate, through interference and resonance, the coordinates of a shared future. This reconfiguration, rooted in the sonic *deterritorializations* theorized by Deleuze and Guattari, dissolves traditional acoustic hierarchies. Sound does not merely describe or occupy pre-established spaces, but deconstructs them, generating hybrid landscapes where the biological and the technological, the human and the non-human, intertwine in

unpredictable flows. This process finds a theoretical ally in Donna Haraway's *Chthulucene*, which invites us to *stay with the trouble*⁸⁷, weaving tentacular alliances beyond species-centric hierarchies.

In this perspective, listening takes the form of a process of 'becoming-with', a multispecies interweaving that welcomes dissonance and disagreement as generative conditions. Birds, batteries, Wi-Fi networks, river flows, and industrial noises come together in a soundscape that rejects the pursuit of harmony as an ultimate goal, favoring instead the productive tension of conflict and the situated response. It is through this radical practice of 'staying in touch with the problem' that sound art contributes to transforming the collapse of the Anthropocene into a possibility for terrestrial coexistence, nourished by the *compost* of unexpected connections and collective care for the future.

1. Paul J. Crutzen, Eugene F. Stoermer, *The 'Anthropocene'*, Global Change Newsletter, (41), 2000, pp. 17-18. See also Donna Haraway, *Anthropocene, Capitalocene, Plantationocene, Chthulucene: Making Kin*, Environmental Humanities, VI, 2015, pp. 159-165.

2. *A Sonic Anthropocene: Sound Practices in a Changing Environment*, Cadernos de Arte e Antropologia, special issue *The Sound of Anthropocene* (2024), ed. by Wilfried Agricola de Cologne, X (1), 2021, pp. 3-17.

3. Gilles Deleuze, Félix Guattari, *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, Italian translation by Paolo Vignola, Naples, Orthotes, 2003.

4. Anja Vandso, *The Sonic Aftermath: The Anthropocene and Interdisciplinarity after the Apocalypse*, in *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Sound Art*, edited by Krogh Groth Sanne, Schulze Holger, London, Bloomsbury Academic, 2020, pp. 21-40.

5. The term *field recording* refers to the practice of recording sound outside of controlled environments, such as studios or laboratories, with the aim capture environmental, natural, or urban sounds in their original context. Originating in ethnography and bioacoustics, *field recording* is now widely used in sound art to explore the situated, ecological, and political dimensions of listening. See Anja Vandsø, *op. cit.*; AM Kanngieser, *Geopolitics and the Anthropocene: Five Propositions for Sound*, "GeoHumanities," I (1), 2015, pp. 80-85.
6. Henry Adam Svec, *Buzzing Lines of Flight: A Survey of My Own Private Soundscape*, "Cadernos de Arte e Antropologia," X (1)A, 2021, pp. 18–25.
7. Vadim Keylin, *Participatory Sound Art: Technologies, Aesthetics, Politics*, Singapore, Palgrave Macmillan, 2023.
8. Salomé Voegelín, *The Political Possibility of Sound: Fragments of Listening*, London, Bloomsbury Academic, 2018.
9. The metaphor of *digging* suggests that listening delves into the materiality of the world, uncovering a 'hidden' (or inaudible) potential. Thus, sound encourages a form of speculative yet concrete thinking, combining sensitivity to phenomena with openness to what still eludes us. *Ibid.*, pp. 151-184.
10. Karen Barad elaborates on 'agential realism' by integrating quantum physics, philosophy of science, and feminist theory, in dialogue with Bohr, Foucault, and Butler. In opposition to representationalism, which presupposes pre-existing entities, Barad argues that reality emerges through 'intra-actions' in which entities co-constitute each other. Matter is conceived as an active agent, intertwined with discourses and apparatuses in *entangled* configurations. See Karen Barad, *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*, Durham, Duke University Press, 2007, pp. 136-139; Karen Barad, *Performativity of Nature. Quantum and Queer*, ed. Elena Bougleux, Italian trans. Restituta Castiello, Pisa, Edizioni ETS, 2017 pp. 63-65.
11. Jane Bennett proposes a vitalist ontology that recognizes agency in matter, challenging the separation between human and non-human. Inspired by Spinoza, Deleuze, and Latour, she invites us to rethink political ecology as a network of material forces. See Jane Bennett, *Vibrant Matter: A Political Ecology of Things*, trans. Angela Balzano, Palermo, Timeo, 2023.
12. Brandon LaBelle, *Sonic Agency: Sound and Emergent Forms of Resistance*, London, Goldsmiths Press, 2018.
13. *Ibid.*, see the chapter *Unlikely Publics: On the Edge of Appearance*, pp. 1–28.
14. Gilles Deleuze, Félix Guattari, *op. cit.*
15. *Ibid.*, p. 484.
16. *Ibid.*, p. 485.
17. *Ibid.*
18. *Ibid.*, p. 630.
19. The humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) is a species of large cetacean belonging to the Balaenopteridae family, known for its complex songs, structured in articulated sequences of sounds that play a fundamental role in communication and social rituals, particularly during the breeding season.
20. David Rothenberg, *Bug Music: How Insects Gave Us Rhythm and Noise*, New York, Picador-St. Martin's Press, 2014.
21. Id., *Survival of the Beautiful: Art, Science, and Evolution*, New York, Bloomsbury Press, 2015.
22. Id., *Nightingales in Berlin: Searching for the Perfect Sound*, Chicago-London, University of Chicago Press, 2019.
23. Id. cited in Louisa Collenberg, *Sonic Becomings: Rhythmic Encounters in Interspecies Improvisation*, "Open Philosophy," IV (1), 2021, cited, p. 226.
24. *Ibid.*, p. 227.
25. *Ibid.*, p. 229.
26. François Bonnet, cited in Laura Collenberg, *Sonic Becomings: Rhythmic Encounters in Interspecies Improvisation*, "Open Philosophy," IV (1), 2021, cit., p. 229.
27. Kim-Cohen Seth, *Against Ambience and Other Essays*, New York, Bloomsbury Academic, 2016, p. 148.
28. *Ibid.*, p. 42. See also Seth Kim-Cohen, interviewed by Mark Perer Wright *Ibid.*, p. 185.
29. The concept "E... E... E..." expresses a logic of connection and continuous variation, as opposed to the logic of identity and representation of the verb "to be." Instead of fixing meanings, 'E' acts as a linguistic tensor that intensifies language, deterritorializes it, and transforms it into an open and multiple flow. See Gilles Deleuze, Félix Guattari, *op. cit.*, p. 155.
30. Kim-Cohen Seth, *op. cit.*, p. 29. See also Kim-Cohen Seth, *In the Blink of an Ear: Toward a Non-Cochlear Sonic Art*, New York, London, The Continuum International Publishing Group, 2009.
31. Bernie L. Krause, *The Great Animal Orchestra: Finding the Origins of Music in the World's Wild Places*, New York, Back Bay Books, 2012, p. 68.
32. *Ibid.*
33. *Ibid.*, p. 249.
34. This study consolidates the ecology of the soundscape, integrating acoustic ecology and bioacoustics. By analyzing soundscapes (biophony, geophony,

anthropophony) with automated recordings and spectrographs, the authors demonstrate variations in sound diversity between ecosystems, influenced by human disturbance. The article proposes soundscapes as indicators of biodiversity and monitoring tools, relevant to sound art in the Anthropocene. See *Soundscape Ecology: The Science of Sound in the Landscape*, "BioScience," LXI (3), 2011, pp. 203–216; What is Soundscape Ecology? An Introduction and Overview of an Emerging New Science, *Landscape Ecology*, XXVI (9), 2011, pp. 1213–1232.

35. Krause's compositions can be explored on the website dedicated to *The Great Animal Orchestra* project, available at <https://www.legrandorchestredesanimaux.com/en/> (last accessed 20/4/2025).

36. The installation was subsequently presented at the *XXII International Exhibition* at the Triennale in Milan, entitled *Broken Nature: Design Takes on Human Survival* (March 1–September 1, 2019).

37. Bernie Krause, United Visual Artists, *The Great Animal Orchestra: Bernie Krause and United Visual Artists*, Paris, Fondation Cartier pour l'Art Contemporain, 2019.

38. Vinciane Despret, *Figures de la re-composition*, in *Le Grand Orchestre des Animaux*, Paris, Actes Sud - Fondation Cartier pour l'art contemporain, 2016, pp. 2–12. For further information, see Vinciane Despret, *What Would Animals Say If We Asked the Right Questions?*, Minneapolis, University of Minnesota Press, 2016, in which she explores animal behavior and how it challenges

human conceptions. Another relevant text is *Our Grateful Dead: Stories of Those Left Behind*, Minneapolis, University of Minnesota Press, 2021 (English translation by Stephen Muecke), which discusses discussion the way animals communicate and interact with humans, and *Penser comme un rat, Versailles*, Éditions Quae, 2016, which analyzes scientific practices through animal behavior.

39. See Bruno Latour, *La société comme possession – la preuve par l'orchestre*, in *Philosophie des possessions*, ed. Didier Debaise, Dijon, Presses du Réel, 2011.

40. Bernie L. Krause, *op. cit.*, p. 10.

41. Mark Peter Wright, *Listening After Nature. Field Recording, Ecology, Critical Practice*, London, Bloomsbury Academic, 2022.

42. *Ibid.*, p. 47.

43. *Ibid.*, pp. 47–48.

44. *Ibid.*, p. 48.

45. *Ibid.*, pp. 44–49; 95–98.

46. *Ibid.*, n.b.

47. *Ibid.*

48. See the chapter *La composizione ecoacustica (Ecoacoustic Composition)* in David Monacchi, *L'arca dei suoni originari. Salvare il canto delle foreste dall'estinzione* (The Ark of Original Sounds: Saving the Song of the Forests from Extinction), Milan, Mondadori, 2019.

49. The project has been exhibited in various venues, including the ZKM in Karlsruhe (2022) and MAXXI in Rome (2022).

50. Deleuze and Guattari's *body without organs* (CsO) should not be understood as an organic entity without physical organs, but as a field of intensity in which vital flows are not yet codified into hierarchical or functional structures.

It is a theoretical figure that resists the molar organization of life, opposing social, biological, and semiotic stratifications. In this sense, a natural environment can be thought of as a body without organs when it is considered in its pure power of relational flows, without yet being converted into an object of appropriation, representation, or archiving. See the chapter

6. *How to Make a Body Without Organs* in Gilles Deleuze, Félix Guattari, *op. cit.*, pp. 227–248.

51. Mark Peter Wright introduces the concept of *elsewhere fields* to describe the multiple dimensions—practical, spatial, technological, conceptual—that mediate and restructure the experience of *field recording*. It is not only about the physical movements of the sound engineer, but also about geopolitical networks, technological devices (hard disks, editing studios, publications), stories, and possible future sound stratifications that traverse and transform landscapes. *Elsewhere fields* thus problematize the idea of direct listening to nature, making visible the logics of mediation, exchange, and re-territorialization inherent in every sound practice. See Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, pp. 5–6.

52. Brandon LaBelle, *op. cit.*

53. *A Sound Map of the Hudson River* (1982) sound installation, 2h. Commissioned by the Hudson River Museum and available at www.anealockwood.com/compositions/ (last accessed 4/20/2025).

54. *A Sound Map of the Danube 1.1 sound installation* (2005), available at www.anealockwood.com/compositions/a-sound-map-of-the-danube/ (last accessed 20/4/2025).

55. *A Sound Map of the Housatonic River 4-channel sound installation* (2010), available at <https://www.anealockwood.com/compositions/a-sound-map-of-the-housatonic-river/> (last accessed 20/4/2025).

56. Cathy Lane, Angus Carlyle, *In the Field: The Art of Field Recording*, Axminster, Uniformbooks, 2014, p. 35.

57. *Ibid.*, p. 34.

58. *Ibid.*, p. 35
59. *Ibid.*, p. 36.
60. Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, p. 97
61. *Ibid.*, p. 99.
62. Stefan Helmreich, *Sounding the Limits of Life: Essays in the Anthropology of Biology and Beyond*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2016, p. 224. 63. *Ibid.*, p. 98.
64. Salomé Voegelin, *op. cit.*
65. *Ibid.*, p. 129.
66. Stefan Helmreich, *op. cit.*, p. 223.
67. *Ibid.*, p. 151.
68. Christina Kubisch, *Electrical Walks*, <https://www.electricalwalks.org> (last accessed 4/30/2025).
69. Ead. in Cox Christoph, *Invisible Cities: An Interview with Christina Kubisch*, "Cabinet," (21), summer 2006, now in Vadim Keylin, *op. cit.*, p. 117. 70. *Ibid.*, p. 116.
71. *Ibid.*, p. 79.
72. See Kim-Cohen, *op. cit.*, p. 111.
73. Mark Peter Wright, Angus Carlyle, *Disonant Doppelganger: Performing the Post-Natural Through Modulated Foley Techniques*, "Cadenos de Arte e Antropologia," X (1), 2021, pp. 37–47.
74. This concept is found in Le Guin's reflections on the need to expand the notion of language to include matter and material itself. According to this view, language is not limited to words or signs, but extends to the material world, and this expansion can occur specifically through sound. See Ursula K. Le Guin, *A Non-Euclidean View of California as a Cold Place to be*, New Haven, Yale University Press, 1983.
75. Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, p. 76. As the author points out, the notion is inspired by Donna Haraway's essay *The Promises of Monsters* (1992), as well as by eco-critical literature and monster studies, p. 32.
76. The graphic score accompanying the work is not a traditional musical score, but a visual-conceptual composition: a sort of 'performative map' that accompanies the experience of listening to the vinyl and suggests a non-linear, tactile, and speculative way of relating to and reinterpreting the soundscapes constructed by the two artists.
77. *Foley art* is a cinematographic technique that originated in the 1920s, devised by Jack Foley, a sound technician at Universal Studios, to create sound effects synchronized with images through the use of everyday objects. See Michel Chion, *Audio-Vision: Sound on Screen*, New York, Columbia University Press, 1994; Rick Altman, *Sound Theory, Sound Practice*, New York, Routledge, 1992. Wright proposes *Foley* as a practice of *sonic fiction* that "helps lift the curtain on field recording. It resists greenwashing the field as somehow separate, outdoors, and over there." Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, pp. 75-76.
78. *Frozen Planet* (2011-2012), a seven-part documentary series produced by the BBC, directed by Vanessa Berlowitz and narrated by David Attenborough, explores the fragility and beauty of the Earth's poles, revealing how frozen landscapes are dynamic ecosystems deeply threatened by climate change.
79. *Planet Earth II* (2016), in six episodes, explores the relationship between animals and extreme environments, highlighting survival strategies in the natural world with an immersive and technologically advanced approach that enhances the spectacular nature of the landscapes as a form of ecological empathy.
80. *Seven Worlds, One Planet* (2019), a seven-episode documentary series produced by the BBC, directed by Scott Alexander and narrated by David Attenborough, offers a geo-biological narrative that divides Earth's biodiversity according to the seven continents, highlighting local evolutionary specificities and the global environmental impacts of human activity.
81. Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, p. 71.
82. *Ibid.*, p. 72.
83. Robert Mendick, Edward Malnick, *BBC accused of routine 'fakery' in wildlife documentaries*, "The Telegraph," December 18, 2011.
84. Mark Peter Wright, *op. cit.*, p. 4.
85. *Ibid.*, pp. 34-38.
86. Baudrillard describes three orders of simulacra, with the fourth phase of the third order – "an image with no relation to any reality" (p. 66) – characterizing the pure simulacrum. Jean Baudrillard, *Simulacra and Simulation. Beasts, Beauvoir, Appearances and Other Objects*, ed. Matteo G. Brega, Milan, Pirego Edizioni, 2024.
87. As is well known, Haraway introduces this concept to describe an ethical and ontological attitude that rejects both nostalgia for an idealized past and the utopia of a salvific future. Staying in touch with the problem means inhabiting the present in its multispecies complexity, accepting disorder, vulnerability, and interconnection as necessary conditions for generating shared forms of life on a damaged Earth. See the chapter *Simpoesis. Symbiogenesis and the art of staying with the trouble*, Donna Haraway, *Chthulucene: Surviving on an Infected Planet*, trans. by C. Durastanti and C. Ciccioni, Rome, Nero, 2020, pp. 89-144.

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